

Relationship between corporate governance and stock price in Nepalese commercial banks

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Abstract

The study examines the relationship between corporate governance and stock price in Nepalese commercial banks. The stock price and stock return are the dependent variables. The selected independent variables are board size, board independence, audit committee size, ownership structure, board meeting, board diversification, firm size, earning per share, and leverage. This study is based on the secondary source of data for the period of 2013/14 to 2019/20 of 20 commercial banks, leading to a total of 140 observations. The regression models are estimated to test the significance and impact of corporate governance on the stock price in Nepalese commercial banks.

The study reveals that board size has a positive impact on stock price. It indicates that increase in board size leads to increase in stock price. Likewise, ownership structure has a positive impact on stock price. It states that increase in foreign ownership leads to increase in stock price. Similarly, board diversification has a positive impact on stock price. It reveals that higher the number of female director on board, higher will be the stock price. Similarly, earnings per share has a positive impact on stock price, which implies that increase in earnings per share leads to increase in stock price. Likewise, leverage has a positive impact on stock price. It shows that increase in leverage lead to increase in stock price. Similarly, firm size also has a positive impact on stock price. It means that the larger the firm size, higher would be the stock price. However board independence, audit committee size, and board meeting have negative impact on stock price. It shows that increase in board independence, audit committee size, and board meeting leads to decrease in stock price. The result also shows that board size, board diversification, EPS, leverage, and firm size have positive impact on stock return. It indicates that increase in board size, board diversification, EPS, leverage, and firm size leads to increase in stock return. However, board independence, ownership structure, board meeting, and audit committee size have negative impact on stock return. It implies that increase in board independence, ownership structure, board meeting, and audit committee size leads to decrease in stock return.

Key words; *Stock price, stock return, board size, board independence, ownership structure, audit committee size, board meeting, board diversification, earning per share, leverage, and firm size.*

1. Introduction

The concept of corporate governance has assumed increasing public interest in recent years. (Silwal, 2016). Corporate governance is defined as the structure and processes by which companies are directed and controlled (Tsamenyi *et al.*, 2007). Shahid and Abbas (2019) defined that the purpose of the corporate governance is to facilitate effective, entrepreneurial and well-judged management that can deliver the long-term success of the company. Similarly, Fremond and Capaul (2002) defined corporate governance as “property rights of shareholders and the mechanisms of exercising such rights”. Shaheen and Nishat (2005) considered it as the practice and arrangement through which a firm’s business is run with the final objective of increasing

shareholder's wealth. Likewise, Mohamed and Elewa (2016) indicated that firms with strong corporate governance have a significant impact on stock prices while it has no significant impact on trade volume. Likewise, Alnodel and Azid (2021) suggested that the power distance between the board and regulators could affect the effectiveness of corporate governance by providing insight into how regulators can improve the efficiency of corporate governance.

According to Gulzar and Wang (2010), good corporate governance is very important for the continuity and sustainability of the businesses that maintain economic growth. Malik (2012) argued that better governed firms have higher stock price because of the fact that better managed firms will perform better and as result stock prices will increase. Farida *et al.* (2019) opined that corporate governance is a process used by company managers to increase corporate accountability in realizing value to shareholders in the long run to consider the interests of the company. Bae & Goyal (2010) stated that the companies managed with good governance have an effect on the increase in stock price. Nguyen *et al.* (2020) found that corporate governance has a significant positive impact on stock price. Huang *et al.* (2011) revealed that there is a positive effect of corporate governance on stock prices and can reduce the volatility of stock prices.

Corporate governance seeks to prevent manipulation, fraud and deception and reduces the negative impact of information asymmetries by setting out control measures in the firm to meet the interests of different stakeholders (Zidan, 2005). Similarly, Idolor and Abdulganiyu (2015) found that the stock market is informationally efficient in Nigeria and that investors do react to the announcement of corporate governance failure. Christian *et al.* (2020) concluded that the number of boards of commissioner meeting, the numbers of directors, Earnings Per Share (EPS), Price to Earnings Ratio (PER) have a positive effect on stock price however, the number of independent commissioner and the number of the board of the directors meeting have negative effect on the stock price. Naveed and Ramzan (2013) revealed that the size has a positive and significant relationship with the share price while the other variables (dividend yield, asset growth, and return on assets) have insignificant relationship with stock price.

Similarly, Tseng *et al.* (2019) found that transparency, anti-corruption, and board diversity were the two most important criteria of corporate governance. Ur-Rehman *et al.* (2010) showed that firms with high percentage of independent directors use more debt. The study also showed that there is a positive relationship between board independence and leverage which implies that independent directors can improve the credibility of the company and its ability to borrow. Truong and Thuy (2021) confirmed a negative relationship between the ownership of foreign investor's stock return on Vietnam stock market. Rubin and Smith (2009) found a negative relationship between the level of ownership and the volatility of stock return.

Claessens and Yurtoglu (2013) described that an effective system of governance is useful for companies with access to finance, better financial output, and desired output for stakeholders. Al-Kassar and Al-Nidawiy (2014) found that there is a positive relationship of board ownership with company's shares and stock prices. Similarly, Christiawan and Tarigan (2007) concluded that there is no significant difference between the performance of the company with managerial ownership and the one without. However, the average company performance is slightly better with the managerial ownership. Guo and Platikanov (2019) found that institutional ownership positively influences the company performance.

Likewise, Uzun *et al.* (2004) found that the board of directors' independence and its committees result in lower corporate fraud. Uwuigbe (2013) indicated that there was a negative relationship of firm ownership structure on firm share prices and there is a positive relation of firm audit committee with firm share prices. Similarly, Karamoy and Tulung (2020) found that the institutional ownership and the composition of the independent commissioner does not significantly influence the stock price of the non-bank financial industry. Similarly, Prabowo *et al.* (2020) indicated that the independent commissioner and managerial ownership have positive and significant impact on stock price while the institutional ownership have negative impact on stock price. Nguyen *et al.* (2020) admitted that the companies with good corporate governance have higher payouts. Likewise, Sharma and Singh (2006) concluded that EPS is the most important determinant of share price. Hunjra *et al.* (2020) suggested that concentrated owners have more power and incentive to ensure the liquidity of the stock market and have insignificant impact of earnings management on stock market liquidity. In emerging economies, ownership concentration negatively affects the stock market liquidity (Yosef and Prencipe, 2013).

Ayesha *et al.* (2014) found that the corporate governance measures have a significant relationship with the EPS of the manufacturing companies. Black *et al.* (2006) explained there is no strong evidence that better-governed firms are more profitable. According to Yermack (1996), the smaller board size was more efficient than the larger board size to obtain higher market valuation, ROE, and ROA. Dahya and McConnell (2007) showed that smaller board size was better for improving firm's performance. However, Hermalin and Weisbach (2003) identified that an increase in board size has a negative effect on market price per share (MPS). Belkhir (2009) confirmed a positive association of size of the board with performance. Likewise, Mahmood and Malik (2007) found that foreign holding is positively and significantly related to the firm performance as measured by firm's holding period returns and Tobin's Q. Aharon & Yagil (2019) revealed that the variance of stock return is positively related to firm's financial leverage.

In context of Nepal, Budha (2016) showed that the board size, board meeting, independent directors, female directors, and non-performing loan have negative impact on market price per share of Nepalese commercial banks. However, CEO duality, executive pay, and leverage have positive impact on MPS of Nepalese commercial bank. Poudel and Hovey (2012) showed that bigger board and audit committee size and lower frequency of board meeting and lower proportion of institutional ownership led to better efficiency in the commercial banks. Bhattarai (2014) showed that earning per share has a significant positive association with share price. Pradhan (2003) found that the payments of dividends and stock prices have strong correlation, however retained earnings has a weak correlation with stock prices.

Likewise, Pradhan and Dahal (2016) showed that the size is the most important determinant that affects the share price. Likewise, Thapa (2019) concluded that dividend and short-term interest rate were the most important predictors of the stock prices in the secondary market of Nepal. Maharjan (2019) concluded that the board meeting and audit committee have positive impact on firm performance. Acharya *et al.* (2015) revealed that the impact of board size, board independence and audit committee are positively insignificant with return on assets whereas debt to equity and firm size has insignificant effect on return on assets.

The above discussion reveals that there is no consistency in the findings of various studies concerning the corporate governance and stock price. Though there are above mentioned empirical evidences in the context of other countries and in Nepal, no such findings using more recent data

exist in the context of Nepal. Therefore, the study has been carried out to analyse the relationship between corporate governance and stock price in Nepalese commercial banks.

Specifically, this study focuses on examining the impact of board size, board independence, ownership structure, audit committee size, board meeting, board diversification, earning per share, leverage, and firm size on stock price and stock return of Nepalese commercial banks.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. Section two describes the sample, data and methodology. Section three presents the empirical results and the final section draws the conclusion.

2. Methodological aspects

The study is based on the secondary data of 20 commercial banks for the period of 2013/14 to 2019/20, leading to a total of 140 observations. The main sources of the data include the annual financial reports of selected commercial banks and Quarterly Economic Bulletin published by Nepal Rastra Bank. Table 1 shows the number of commercial banks selected for the study along with the study time period and number of observations.

Table 1: List of sample banks along with the study period and number of observations

S.N.	Name of Banks	Study period	Observations
1	Everest Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
2	Nabil Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
3	Prime Commercial Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
4	Nepal Bangladesh Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
5	Century Commercial Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
6	Prabhu Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
7	Nepal Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
8	Civil Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
9	Siddhartha Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
10	NMB Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
11	Machhapuchchhre Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
12	Sanima Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
13	Himalayan Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
14	Sunrise Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
15	Kumari Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
16	Laxmi Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
17	Global IME Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
18	Nepal SBI Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
19	NIC Asia Bank Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
20	Bank of Kathmandu Limited	2013/14 to 2019/20	7
Total number of Observations			140

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Thus, the study is based on 140 observations.

The model

The model estimated in the study assumes that stock price and stock return depends upon audit committee size, board size, board independence, board meeting, board diversification, earning per share, leverage, firm size, and ownership structure. Therefore, the model takes the following form:

$$SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 OS_{it} + \beta_4 AC_{it} + \beta_5 BM_{it} + \beta_6 BD_{it} + \beta_7 EPS_{it} + \beta_8 L_{it} + \beta_9 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$SR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 OS_{it} + \beta_4 AC_{it} + \beta_5 BM_{it} + \beta_6 BD_{it} + \beta_7 EPS_{it} + \beta_8 L_{it} + \beta_9 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where,

SP = Stock price per share, defined as the average price of closing and opening share price,
In rupees.

SR = Stock return, defined as the capital gain yield, in percentage.

BS = Board size, defined as the number of board member in board.

BI = Board Independence, defined as the number of independent director on board.

OS = Ownership structure takes the value 1 if there is a foreign ownership, otherwise 0.

ACS = Audit committee size, defined as the number of audit committee members.

BM = Board meeting, defined as a total number of meeting held in a fiscal year.

BD = Board diversification, defined as the number of female director on board.

EPS = Earnings per share, defined as net profit divided by the number of common shares outstanding.

L = Leverage, defined as total liability to total assets, in percentage.

FS = Firm size, defined as the natural logarithm of total assets, Rupees in billion.

The following section describes the independent variables used in the study along with the hypothesis formulation:

Board size

Board size is the total number of directors on a board. Pradhan (2014) found that there is a positive and significant impact of board size on stock return. Lakatos (2020) showed that board size has a positive impact on firms' performance. Similarly, Wu (2003) confirmed that there is a positive relationship between larger board size and performance of the firms. Kalsie and Shrivastav (2016) concluded that the board size has a positive and significant impact on the firm performance. Butar (2019) suggested that larger board size plays a significant role in improving the quality of financial reporting. Based on discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₁: There is a positive relationship between board size and stock price.

H₂: There is a positive relationship between board size and stock return.

Board independence

Ararat *et al.* (2010) showed a negative relationship between an independent board member and firm performance. Bhagat & Black (2001) concluded that there is a negative relationship between board independence and firm's value. Rashid (2009) found that board independence and firm economic performance does not positively influence each other. According to Grace (1995) found there is a negative relationship board independence and firm performance in Anglo American countries. Fuzi *et al.* (2016) showed a negative relationship between the independent director and return on stock which is an indicator of firm performance. Bird *et al.* (2018) found that board

independence have negative associations with monthly stock return. Based on discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₃: There is a negative relationship between board independent and stock price.

H₄: There is a negative relationship between board independent and stock return.

Ownership structure

Lubatkin & Chatterjee (1994) found that there is a positive relationship between ownership structure of the company and capital structure decisions. According to Douma *et al.* (2002) revealed a positive and significant correlation between firm performance and foreign ownership. Nguyen *et al.* (2020b) found that the foreign ownership ratio has a positive impact on the financial performance. Similarly, Park (2004) found that foreign ownership has a positive impact on Tobin's Q ratio. Nguyen & Pham (2017) showed that foreign ownership in Vietnam has a positive impact on financial performance. Vo (2015) confirmed that the foreign ownership decreases firm stock price volatility in Vietnam stock market. Based on the discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₅: There is a positive relationship between ownership structure and stock price.

H₆: There is a positive relationship between ownership structure and stock return.

Audit committee size

Afza and Nazir (2014) showed that there is a significant negative relationship between the size of an audit committee and firm performance because there is little room for flexibility in a larger committee. Lisic *et al.* (2011) found negative associations between audit committee and financial expertise. Vafeas (1999) found that large audit committee can negatively affect the share price or performance of the firm. Yamchi *et al.* (2013) showed the negative relationship between audit committee and shareholders value. According to Al-Mamun *et al.* (2014) concluded that audit committee size has a negative relationship with performance of the firm. Based on discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₇: There is a negative relationship between audit committee size and stock price.

H₈: There is a negative relationship between audit committee size and stock return.

Board diversification

Adams & Ferreira (2009) found that the presence of female directors has positive impact on firm performance. Mijntje (2013) revealed that women directors have positive impact on the board performance. According to Carter *et al.* (2003), failure to choose the most suitable candidate affects company performance and the absence of women might be suboptimal for the firm. Diversity might also contribute to the discussion, exchange of ideas and performance of the group (Kang *et al.* 2007). Lückcrath-Rovers (2013) showed presence of a woman on the board and the percentage of women on the board are significantly and positively correlated with ROE. Gul *et al.* (2011) found that gender diversity improves stock price informativeness through the mechanism of increased public disclosure in large firms and by encouraging private information collection in small firms. Green & Homroy (2018) revealed a positive effect of female director on firm performance. Based on discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₉: There is a positive relationship between board diversification and stock price.

H₁₀: There is a positive relationship between board diversification and stock return.

Board meeting

Vafeas (1999) found that annual number of board meetings is inversely related to firm value. It implies that increase in number of board meetings decreases the share price. Lin *et al.* (2014) showed that board attendance decreases with multiple directorships, meeting frequency, and board size, indicating that busier directors and a more complex board combine to lower meeting attendance. Aryani *et al.* (2017) revealed that the number of board meetings does not affect the company's performance. Board diligence in terms of board meetings is found to have an adverse effect on firm performance (Johl *et al.*, 2015). Evans *et al.* (2002) found that increasing board meeting frequency significantly respond to poor performance. Based on discussion, it develops the following hypothesis:

H₁₁: There is a negative relationship between board meeting and stock price.

H₁₂: There is a negative relationship between board meeting and stock return.

Earnings per share

According to Muhammad & Scrimgeour (2014), there is a positive and significant relationship between EPS and stock prices. Baskin (1989) found that the earning per share has a positive relationship with market price which indicates higher the earning per share, higher will be the market price. Bhatt & Sumangala (2012) confirmed that EPS and market value of equity share are positively related. Sharma (2011) revealed that earning per share has a significant positive impact on the market price of share. Uddin & Rahman (2013) observed that the EPS has the highest positive impact on the stock price of the companies. Khan & Aamir (2011) found that there is a positive relationship of earnings per share, profit after tax and return on equity with stock price. Purwaningrat & Suaryana (2015) found that earnings per share has a positive and significant effect on stock return. Based on discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₁₃: There is a positive relationship between EPS and stock price.

H₁₄: There is a positive relationship between EPS and stock return.

Leverage

Weill (2003) argued that leverage is one of the proxies of corporate performance. Fosu (2013) found that there is significant positive impact of financial leverage on firms' performance in context of Africa. Di Patti & Berger (2006) reported that higher leverage is related to higher performance. Sharma (2006) found that there is a positive relationship between firm value and financial leverage. Adeyemi & Collins (2011) found that the market value of a firm is positively influenced by the choice of financial leverage (capital structure). Ramla (2021) found that leverage has a positive and significant effect on returns on stock. Acheampong (2014) concluded that there is a positive relationship between leverage and stock return. Hussan (2016) revealed that debt financing also increases share price of the firm which indicates positive profit earning ability as well as wealth maximization. Based on discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₁₅: There is a positive relationship between leverage and stock price.

H₁₆: There is a positive relationship between leverage and stock return.

Firm size

Firm size refers to total assets of the company. Pradhan and Dahal (2016) showed that size is found to be the most important determining variable that affects the share price. Naveed and Ramzan (2013) showed that size has a positive significant relationship with the share price. Srinivasan (2012) revealed that firm size have a positive and significant impact on the share price of commercial banks. Prater & Ghosh (2006) stated that larger firm size have better performance as

they are able to diversify their risk. Chen and Zhang (1998) revealed that there is a positive relationship between firm size and stock returns. Almunani (2014) concluded that the size, price earnings ratio and EPS are the most important determinants of stock price. Sugiarto (2011) showed that the firm size has a positive effect on stock prices. Based on discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis:

H₁₇: There is a positive relationship between firm size and stock price.

H₁₈: There is a positive relationship between firm size and stock return.

3. Results and discussions

Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of selected dependent and independent variables during the period 2013/14 to 2019/20.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

This table shows the descriptive statistics of dependent and independent variables of 20 commercial banks of Nepal for the study period 2013/14 to 2019/20. The dependent variables are SP (Stock price is measured by the average of opening and closing stock price of the bank, in rupees) and SR (Stock return is measured by the capital gain yield, in percentage). The independent variables are BS (Board size, defined as the number of board member in board), BI (Board Independence, defined as the number of independent director on board), OS (Ownership structure takes the value 1 if there is a foreign ownership, otherwise 0), ACS (Audit committee size, defined as the number of member in audit committee), BM (Board meeting, defined as a total number of meeting held in a fiscal year), BD (Board diversification, defined as the number of female director on board) EPS (Earning per share is measured by the profit dividend by outstanding share of common stock, in rupees), LEV (Leverage is measured as total debt to total assets, in percentage) and FS (Firm size is measured as the natural logarithm of total assets of individual sample commercial banks for particular year, in billion).

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.
SP	139.00	3385.00	571.66	508.66
SR	-1.00	1.84	0.05	.5250
BS	5.00	11.00	7.15	1.28
BI	0.00	1.00	0.62	0.48
OS	0.00	1.00	0.35	0.47
ACS	1.00	5.00	3.21	0.59
BM	12.00	54.00	22.36	8.41
BD	0.00	34.00	0.63	2.91
EPS	4.35	86.04	25.37	14.36
LEV	19.39	97.70	88.48	6.50
FS	19.22	26.34	24.87	1.10

Correlation analysis

Having indicated the descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation coefficients are computed and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Pearson's Correlation coefficient matrix

This table shows the bi-variant Pearson's correlation coefficients of dependent and independent variables of commercial banks of Nepal for the study period of 2070/71 to 2076/77. The dependent variables are SP (Stock price is measured by the average of opening and closing stock price of the bank, in rupees) and SR (Stock return is measured by the capital gain yield, in percentage). The independent variables are BS (Board size, defined as the number of board member in board), BI (Board Independence, defined as the number of independent director on board), OS (Ownership structure takes the value 1 if there is a foreign ownership, otherwise 0), ACS (Audit committee size, defined as the number of member in audit committee), BM (Board meeting, defined as a total number of meeting held in a fiscal year), BD (Board diversification, defined as the number of female director on board) EPS (Earning per share is measured by the profit dividend by outstanding share of common stock, in rupees), LEV (Leverage is measured as total debt to total assets, in percentage), and FS (Firm size is measured as the natural logarithm of total assets of individual sample commercial banks for particular year, in billion).

Variables	SP	SR	BS	BI	OS	ACS	BM	BD	EPS	LEV	FS
SP	1										
SR	0.261**	1									
BS	0.205*	0.296**	1								
BI	-0.246**	-0.238**	-0.135	1							
OS	0.436**	-0.010	0.214*	0.171*	1						
ACS	-0.011	-0.002	0.134	0.207*	0.063	1					
BM	-0.297**	-0.147	0.153	0.266**	-0.275**	0.077	1				
BD	0.023	0.159	0.069	-0.047	-0.085	-0.066	0.050	1			
EPS	0.836**	0.108	0.127	-0.155	0.386**	-0.012	-0.311**	-0.041	1		
LEV	0.215*	0.144	0.031	-0.197*	0.059	-0.017	-0.173*	0.009	0.152	1	
FS	0.125	0.089	-0.241**	0.013	0.214*	-0.025	-0.472**	0.043	0.173*	0.424**	1

Table 3 shows that the board size is positively correlated to stock price. It shows that increase in board size leads to increase in stock price. Likewise, board independence is negatively correlated with stock price. It shows that the higher the number of independent directors, lower would be the stock price. Similarly, ownership structure has a positive relationship with stock price. It implies that increase in foreign ownership leads to increase in stock price. Similarly, there is a negative relationship between audit committee size and stock price. It implies that increase in number of audit committee leads to decrease in share price. Likewise, board meeting is negatively related to stock price. It shows that the higher the number of board meeting, lower would be the stock price. Similarly, board diversification has a positive relationship with stock price. It reveals that increase in number of female director on board leads to increase in stock price. Likewise, earnings per share has a positive relationship with stock price. This states that increase in earnings per share leads to increase in stock price. Similarly, leverage is positively correlated to stock price. It shows that increase in leverage leads to increase in stock price. Moreover, there is a positive relationship between firm size and stock price. It implies that bigger the firm size, higher would be the stock price.

The result also shows that there is a positive relationship between board size and stock return. It implies that increase in board size leads to increase in stock return. However, there is a negative relationship between board independence and stock return. It implies that increase in number of independent director leads to decrease in stock return. Similarly, ownership structure is negatively correlated to stock return. It shows that increase in foreign ownership leads to decrease in stock return. Similarly, there is a negative relationship between audit committee size and stock return. It reveals that greater the number of audit committee members, lower would be the stock return. Likewise, board meeting is negatively related to stock return. It shows that the higher the number of board meeting, lower would be the stock return. Similarly, board diversification has a positive relationship with stock return. It reveals that increase in number of female director on board leads to increase in stock return. Likewise, earnings per share has a positive relationship with stock return. This states that increase in earnings per share leads to increase in stock return. Similarly, leverage is positively correlated to stock return. It shows that increase in leverage leads to increase in stock return. Moreover, there is a negative relationship between firm size and stock price. It implies that bigger the firm size, higher would be the stock return.

Regression analysis

Having indicated the Pearson's correlation coefficients, the regression analysis has been carried out and the results are in the Table 4. More specifically, it shows the regression results of board size, board independence, ownership structure, audit committee, board meeting, board diversification, earning per share, leverage and firm size on stock price.

Table 4: Estimated regression results of board size, board independence, ownership structure, audit committee, board diversification, board meeting, earning per share, leverage and firm size on stock price

The results are based on the data of 20 commercial banks of Nepal with 140 observations for the period of 2070/71 to 2076/77 using linear regression model. The model $SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 OS_{it} + \beta_4 AC_{it} + \beta_5 BM_{it} + \beta_6 BD_{it} + \beta_7 EPS_{it} + \beta_8 LEV_{it} + \beta_9 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$ where the dependent variable is SP (Stock price is measured by the average of opening and closing stock price of the bank, in rupees). The independent variables are BS (Board size, defined as the number of board member in board), BI (Board Independence, defined as the number of independent director on board), OS (Ownership structure takes the value 1 if there is a foreign ownership, otherwise 0), ACS (Audit committee size, defined as the number of member in audit committee), BM (Board meeting, defined as a total number of meeting held in a fiscal year), BD (Board diversification, defined as the number of female director on board) EPS (Earning per share is measured by the profit dividend by outstanding share of common stock, in rupees), LEV (Leverage is measured as total debt to total assets, in percentage), and FS (Firm size is measured as the natural logarithm of total assets of individual sample commercial banks for particular year, in billion).

Model	Intercept	Regression coefficients of									Adj R ²	SEE	F-Value
		BS	BI	OS	AC	BM	BD	EPS	LEV	FS			
1	11.537 (0.048)	81.391 (2.455)*									0.035	499.647	6.029
2	732.923 (10.681)**		-0.480 (2.970)**								0.246	356.230	8.832
3	408.667 (8.438)**			462.395 (5.668)**							0.190	459.476	32.131
4	601.803 (2.536)*				-9.370 (1.290)						0.070	510.491	0.017
5	907.123 (8.267)**					-17.494 (3.642)**					0.696	280.425	317.063
6	574.935 (12.881)**						3.955 (3.267)**				0.082	487.856	13.265
7	176.5074 (3.656)**							29.493 (17.806)**			0.070	512.256	7.011
8	908.391 (1.576)								16.729 (2.574)*		0.046	498.607	6.626
9	863.319 (0.887)									57.674 (1.476)	0.008	506.51	2.179
10	223.809 (0.888)	68.764 (2.098)*	-231.447 (2.673)**								0.077	488.804	6.722
11	432.290 (1.925)	23.560 (0.791)	-331.342 (4.249)**	504.782 (6.313)**							0.282	431.083	19.048
12	394.323 (1.433)	22.357 (0.738)	-335.709 (4.179)**	505.024 (6.294)**	-15.310 (0.240)						0.277	432.595	14.201
13	237.188 (1.367)	20.938 (1.130)	-159.669 (3.162)**	171.879 (3.192)**	-10.320 (0.265)	-4.562 (3.6521)**	2.210 (2.020)*	26.214 (15.017)**			0.73	264.478	75.494
14	684.696 (1.913)	21.548 (1.168)	-146.270 (2.856)**	167.936 (3.127)**	-8.962 (0.231)	-5.621 (2.2620)*	1.102 (3.198)**	25.980 (14.875)**	5.046 (2.427)*		0.743	263.452	63.742
15	23.806 (0.039)	12.790 (0.655)	-144.945 (2.841)**	1842.764 (3.359)**	-9.301 (0.240)	-8.251 (4.331)**	2.039 (2.110)*	26.147 (14.977)**	7.343 (1.873)	32.695 (1.338)	0.733	262.666	55.22

Notes:

- Figures in parenthesis are t-values.
- The asterisk signs (**) and (*) indicate that the results are significant at one percent and five percent level respectively.
- Stock price is the dependent variable.

The regression result shows that the beta coefficients for board size are positive with stock price. It indicates that the board size has a positive impact on the stock price. This finding is similar to the findings of Butar (2019). Likewise, the beta coefficients for board independence are negative with stock price. It shows that the board independence has a negative impact on stock price. This finding is similar to the findings of Ararat *et al.* (2010). Similarly, the beta coefficients for ownership structure are positive with stock price. It reveals that ownership structure has a positive impact on stock price. This finding is similar to the findings of Nguyen & Pham (2017). However, the beta coefficients for audit committee size are negative with stock price. It reveals that audit committee size has a negative impact on stock price. This findings is similar to the findings of Afza and Nazir (2014). Similarly, the beta coefficients for board meeting are negative with stock price. It reveals that number of board meeting has a negative impact on stock price. This findings

is similar to the findings of Johl *et al.* (2015). However, the result reveals that the beta coefficients for board diversification are positive with stock return. It shows that the board diversification has a positive impact on stock price. This findings is similar to the findings of Lückerath-Rovers (2013). Similarly, the beta coefficients for earning price per share are positive with stock price. It indicates that earning price per share has a positive impact on stock price. This finding is similar to Muhammad & Scrimgeour (2014). In addition, the beta coefficients for leverage are positive with stock price. It implies that leverage has a positive impact on stock price. The findings is similar to the findings of Fosu (2013). Likewise, the beta coefficients for firm size are positive with stock price. It indicates that the firm size has a positive impact on the stock price. The findings is similar to findings of Naveed and Ramzan (2013). The result also shows that most of the beta coefficients are significant at five percent level.

Table 5 shows the regression results of board size, board independence, ownership structure, audit committee size, board meeting, board diversification, earning per share, leverage and firm size on stock return.

Table 5: Estimated regression results of board size, board independence, ownership Structure, audit committee, board meeting, board diversification, earning per share, leverage and firm size on stock return

The results are based on the data of 20 commercial banks of Nepal with 140 observations for the period of 2070/71 to 2018/19 using linear regression model. The model $SR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 OS_{it} + \beta_4 ACS_{it} + \beta_5 BM_{it} + \beta_6 BD_{it} + \beta_7 EPS_{it} + \beta_8 L_{it} + \beta_9 FS_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$ where the dependent variable is SR (Stock return is measured by the capital gain yield, in percentage). The independent variables are BS (Board size, defined as the number of board member in board), BI (Board Independence, defined as the number of independent director on board), OS (Ownership structure takes the value 1 if there is a foreign ownership, otherwise 0), ACS (Audit committee size, defined as the number of member in audit committee), BM (Board meeting, defined as a total number of meeting held in a fiscal year), BD (Board diversification, defined as the number of female director on board) EPS (Earning per share is measured by the profit dividend by outstanding share of common stock, in rupees), LEV (Leverage is measured as total debt to total assets, in percentage), and FS (Firm size is measured as the natural logarithm of total assets of individual sample commercial banks for particular year, in billion).

Model	Intercept	Regression coefficients of									Adj R2	SEE	F-Value
		BS	BI	OS	ACS	BM	BD	EPS	LEV	FS			
1	0.812 (3.633)**	0.121 (3.633)**									0.081	0.5032	17.125
2	0.218 (3.070)**		-0.257 (2.869)**								0.5	0.5812	13.2
3	0.061 (1.095)			-0.011 (0.122)							0.007	0.5269	8.23
4	0.062 (0.255)				-0.002 (0.023)						0.007	0.5269	0.015
5	0.262 (2.084)*					-0.190 (2.774)**					0.015	0.5217	3.014
6	0.039 (2.866)**						0.029 (2.073)*				0.013	0.5174	2.981
5	0.044 (0.0481)							0.004 (2.271)*			0.004	0.5238	0.001
6	0.969 (1.606)								0.012 (1.705)		0.014	0.5214	1.615
7	1.109 (1.100)									0.042 (1.045)	0.001	0.5248	2.907
8	0.593 (2.329)*	0.110 (3.306)**	-0.216 (2.463)**								0.114	0.4942	1.092
9	0.610 (2.361)*	0.113 (3.305)**	-0.208 (2.316)**	-0.040 (0.439)							0.109	0.4957	9.878

10	0.617 (1.949)	0.113 (3.41)**	-0.208 (0.193)	-0.040 (0.437)	-0.003 (0.039)						0.102	0.4975	6.611
11	0.681 (2.081)*	0.133 (3.238)**	-0.190 (1.996)	-0.073 (0.721)	-0.002 (0.032)	-0.03 (2.786)**					0.099	0.4982	4.922
12	1.394 (2.056)*	0.114 (3.275)**	-0.168 (1.737)	-0.079 (0.783)	-0.000 (0.002)	-0.002 (2.075)*	0.08 (2.200)*	0.052 (2.102)*	0.102 (2.301)*	0.4974 (1.196)	3.626	0.4652	4.051
13	0.602 (0.522)	0.104 (2.808)**	-0.166 (1.712)	-0.059 (0.566)	-0.001 (0.007)	-0.02 (0.733)	0.11 (1.450)	0.039 (2.230)*	0.101 (3.051)**	0.4979 (2.041)*	3.205	0.5213	4.163

Notes:

- i. Figures in parenthesis are t-values.
- ii. The asterisk signs (**) and (*) indicate that the results are significant at one percent and five percent level respectively.
- iii. Stock return is the dependent variable.

The regression result shows that the beta coefficients for board size are positive with stock return. It indicates that the board size has a positive impact on the stock return. The findings is similar to the findings of Kalsie and Shrivastav (2016). Likewise, the beta coefficients for board independence are negative with stock return. It shows that the board independence has a negative impact on stock return. This finding is similar to Bird *et al.* (2018). Similarly, the beta coefficients for ownership structure are negative with stock return. It reveals that ownership structure has a negative impact on stock return. The findings is not consistent with the hypothesis. In addition, the beta coefficients for audit committee size are negative with stock return. It reveals that audit committee size has a negative impact on stock return. This finding is similar to the findings of Al-Mamun *et al.* (2014). Similarly, the beta coefficients for board meeting are negative with stock return. It implies that board meeting has a negative impact on stock return. The findings is similar to the findings of Lin *et al.* (2014). However, the beta coefficients for board diversification are positive with stock return. It shows that board diversification has a positive impact on stock return. This finding is similar to the findings of Green & Homroy (2018). Likewise, the beta coefficients for EPS are positive with stock return. It shows that EPS has a positive impact on stock return. This finding is similar to the findings of Khan & Aamir (2011). Similarly, the beta coefficients for leverage are positive with stock return. It reveals that leverage has a positive impact on stock return. This finding is similar to the findings of Ramla (2021). In addition, the beta coefficients for firm size are positive with stock return. It implies that firm size has a positive impact on stock return. This finding is similar to the findings of Almumani (2014). The result also shows that the majority of the beta coefficients are significant at five percent level.

4. Summary and conclusion

Stock market is an important part of the economy of a country. The stock market plays a pivotal role in the growth of the industry and commerce of the country that eventually affects the economy of the country to a great extent. An effective system of governance is useful for companies with access to finance, better financial output, and desired output for stakeholders. The stock price in the market is not static rather it change every day. The price of any commodity is affected by corporate governance variables.

The study attempts to analyze the impact of corporate governance on stock price of Nepalese commercial banks. The study is based on secondary data gathered from 20 commercial banks for the period from 2070/71 to 2076/77.

The result shows the board size, ownership structure, board diversification, earning per share, leverage and firm size have positive impact on stock price. However, board independence, audit committee size, and board meeting have negative impact on stock price. In addition, the result also

shows that board size, board diversification, earning per share, leverage and firm size have positive impact on stock return. However, board independence, ownership structure, audit committee size, and board meeting have negative impact on stock return. The study concludes that the ownership structure followed by EPS, board meeting and board independence are the most influencing factor that affects the stock price. The study also concludes that board size is the most influencing factor followed by board independence, board meeting, and EPS that determines the changes in stock return of the Nepalese commercial banks.

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